

AMONG THE POPULATION CARIES AND ITS PREVENTION

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7452736>

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Abstract: Those working in practice, medicine and the Ministry of Health should analyze the diagnosis, treatment among the population and give a detailed and deep answer to caries dental diseases. It is necessary to think deeply which of the work performed will meet the requirements and be used in practice.

So, as a future dentist, I would advise you to take the necessary measures already at the initial stage. Curious patients may have a very interesting question, what if nothing is done? The fact is that if you do not take any measures and do not carry out prevention, the carious process will spread even deeper, cavities will form, various complications may join, and in the worst case, you can lose a tooth.

Practitioners working in medicine and the Ministry of Health should analyze the diagnosis and treatment and give a detailed and in-depth answer.

Keywords: Caries is Latin for decay. Where does caries begin, and why is it dangerous for the population? It begins with damage to the hard tissues of the teeth, namely from the enamel - this is caries.

Ключевые слова: Кариес на латыни означает кариес. Где начинается кариес и чем он опасен для населения? Начинается с поражения твердых тканей зубов, а именно с эмали - это и есть кариес.

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Received: 15-12-2022

Accepted: 17-12-2022

Published: 22-12-2022

Introduction . A fairly popular topic among dentists and a common disease among the population is Caries.

Caries from Latin means decay, and it was not for nothing that they called it that. Where does caries begin, and why is it dangerous for the population?

It begins with damage to the hard tissues of the teeth, namely from the enamel - this is caries. Some people may have a question, why is it dangerous?

After all, at first we do not feel anything. And why is it dangerous if we don't feel anything and nothing bothers us? As a future dentist, I would advise you to take the necessary measures already at the initial stage. Curious patients may have a very interesting question, what if nothing is done? The fact is that if you do not take any measures and do not carry out prevention, the carious process will spread

even deeper, cavities will form, various complications may join, and in the worst case, you can lose a tooth.

As we said earlier, the cause of caries is the destruction of the hard tissues of the tooth. Bacteria have a destructive effect on the hard tissues of the tooth. It is no secret that a large number of various microorganisms live in the human mouth, but what is the problem if we brush our teeth 2 or 3 times a day? But the fact is that these same bacteria after 2-3 hours, even after a thorough brushing of the teeth, they can still reach up to a million in number! They actively attach to the surface and affect the enamel, which causes dental caries. And why then brush your teeth if we can not avoid caries? A very interesting question, with the help of cleaning our teeth, we to some extent slow down the process of bacterial reproduction. We must not allow bacteria to multiply by creating favorable conditions for them. The fastest reproduction occurs in a favorable environment for them, which is formed under different conditions.

Regardless of the factors, the occurrence of caries requires timely treatment. At an early stage, caries can be cured much faster and cheaper. Tooth decay can lead to the need for a complete tooth replacement. The nature of human nutrition has a great influence on the condition of the teeth. Prevention of caries still depends on the way of nutrition. To prevent caries, we follow a few recommendations:

Stages of caries: Speaking about the types of the disease, there is a classification according to the severity of its course and the depth of the pathological lesion. Signs of an acute course are softening of tissues, undermined edges of the carious focus. In the chronic course, there is pigmentation of the lesion site, high tissue density, relatively smooth edges.

Caries classification:

initial - at this stage of development of caries, the disease proceeds without pronounced symptoms and uncomfortable sensations. On the enamel, you can see a chalky, brown or grayish speck;

superficial - a defect forms on the surface, the enamel in the affected area becomes rough to the touch;

medium - the defect is aggravated, the dentin-enamel junction is involved in the pathological process;

deep - dentin is affected at all levels.

caries symptoms

One of the most characteristic signs is the occurrence of bad breath. If there was no timely diagnosis and it was not possible to get rid of the disease in the early stages, over time the patient feels pain at the site of the lesion upon contact with cold, hot or sweet food. Regardless of the type of enamel damage, there are no spontaneous pains.

High risk of complications. By postponing a visit to the dentist, you run the risk of experiencing really unbearable pain - this is how pulpitis feels when the internal structures of the tooth are acutely inflamed. Another possible complication is periodontitis, accompanied by the formation of painful cysts and threatening to remove the affected unit. And caries on the front teeth is also becoming a serious aesthetic problem.

Treatment options

How to get rid of caries? Contact your dentist as soon as possible. The choice of a specific therapeutic tactic will directly depend on the degree of damage. It can be both enamel remineralization and all kinds of reconstructive techniques.

- Improper oral hygiene, especially irregular or ineffective brushing of teeth;
 - Rinse your mouth after eating or use good quality chewing gum to clean your teeth and normalize the acidity in your mouth.
 - Irrational nutrition with an excess of soft carbohydrate foods and a lack of raw vegetables ;
 - reduce the amount of sweets and flour products consumed;
 - select the menu so that the balance of fats, proteins and carbohydrates is appropriate for age and lifestyle;
 - introduce raw vegetables into your daily diet, which will allow you to naturally clean your teeth while eating
 - Hypovitaminosis ;
 - saturate the body with all the necessary vitamins and minerals, if necessary, take multivitamin complexes;
 - Low content in drinking water of some minerals (fluorine, phosphorus and calcium);
 - it is advised to eat fish and some seafood every 3 days, to get phosphorus and vitamin D;
 - it is recommended to introduce fermented milk products into the menu that saturate the body with calcium. For example: cottage cheese, sour cream, curdled milk, fermented baked milk, varenets, acidophilus, yogurt and some cheeses.
- Disease of the gastrointestinal tract.

In some conditions, we ourselves can determine the presence of caries, based on changes in the appearance of the teeth. But for a reliable diagnosis of the disease, it is better to consult a dentist. Certain examinations allow caries to be determined. This is mainly vital staining of enamel, research using ultraviolet radiation, X-ray. Vital staining of enamel With its help, it is possible not only to detect demineralization of the enamel, but also to judge the degree of damage to the enamel. The staining method is based on the fact of increasing the permeability of demineralized enamel for dye (2% methylene blue aqueous solution). The tooth is cleaned of plaque, isolated from saliva with cotton rolls and dried. A dye is applied

to the surface of the tooth for 3 minutes, after which the swab is removed and the excess dye is washed off. The evaluation of enamel staining is carried out either using a special 10-point scale with different shades of blue, or visually, subdividing the intensity of staining into low, medium and high. For diagnostic purposes, a single staining of the enamel is sufficient. To monitor the effectiveness of the treatment, re-staining of the enamel after certain periods of time should be carried out. The method of vital enamel staining is convenient for the differential diagnosis of initial caries from non-carious lesions of the hard tissues of the tooth, such as fluorosis and enamel hypoplasia, in which staining does not occur. This method also serves to determine the need for a repeated course of remineralizing therapy.

UV irradiation. The essence of this study is that in the near-UV spectrum, healthy tissues glow green, and bacterial porphyrins glow red. This high color contrast (green VS red filtered or blue VS pink unfiltered) provides an effective alternative to classic caries-detector stains, allowing more precise dissection of diseased dental tissues, especially in areas of the dentin-enamel junction and close to the dental pulp.

Radiography. This method is used to diagnose caries of contact surfaces. The bite-wing method (interproximal radiography) is mainly used, which allows not only to detect the presence of hidden carious cavities, but also to determine their size.

From the stage of development of caries Depending on the damage to the teeth, the following stages are distinguished: The initial stage is the stain stage , from the beginning there are white foci of demineralization, and after the damaged enamel darkens Superficial caries - demineralization of the surface layer of enamel Medium caries - this is a lesion of the dentin layer lying under the enamel, and then a carious cavity is formed. Deep dental caries - in which demineralization of the deep layers of dentin occurs with the formation of a large and deep cavity in the tooth.

If not treated, what is the danger of caries? If you do not follow the hygiene rules described above, then there is a risk of developing caries of various complications. If nothing is done, then caries can cause a number of other diseases. For example:

- The development of pulpitis - Inflammation of the soft tissues of the tooth is accompanied by severe pain.

- Development of periodontitis - The spread of infection through the channels inside the tooth causes inflammation of adjacent tissues. When a purulent cavity is formed at the roots, a diagnosis of periodontal abscess is established.

- Development of a cyst - During periodontitis, destruction of bone tissue can occur with the growth of granulations and the formation of a cavity among them, which leads to a cyst.

- Development of flux - Severe swelling of the gums or cheeks leads to the development of pus.

Monitor food temperature

- Enamel microdamages can occur not only under the action of bacteria. Too hot or cold food often leads to cracking of the enamel, which contributes to the penetration of infection deep into the tooth and the development of caries.

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